

A new genus of the tribe Cerambycini and a new species of the genus *Neocerambyx* Thomson, 1861 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from China

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Abstract: New synonyms are proposed *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867, **syn. n.** A new genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, **gen. n.** (type species *Neocerambyx grandis* Gahan 1891) is described for 4 species from South-East Asia. A new species *Neocerambyx elenae* Lazarev, **sp. n.** close to *N. atratulus* (Holzschuh 2018) is described from China (Hainan Is.).

Introduction

The species composition of *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867 and *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 were not generally accepted in scientific community. A precise application of morphological diagnosis for both genera shows its identity and necessity of an introduction of a new genus, which is described bellow.

A careful investigation of Cerambycidae materials from South-East Asia, preserved in the collection of S. Murzin (Moscow) showed the existence of a new species from China (Hainan Is.) described below.

Materials and methods

A photograph was taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 - 30.5 mm 1:2.8 - 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP 7X-45X. The photograph was edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20. The type is deposited in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia) [ML].

Results

Genus *Bulbocerambyx* Lazarev, gen. n.

Type species. *Neocerambyx grandis* Gahan 1891

Description. The traditional definitions of *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867 (type species *Cerambyx pascoei* J. Thomson, 1857) and *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 (type species *Cerambyx paris* Wiedemann, 1821) are not adequate. It was generally accepted that males of *Neocerambyx* have strongly swollen 3rd - 4th antennal joints and 3rd joint not much longer than 4th. In males of *Massicus* 3rd - 4th antennal joints are not swollen and 3rd joint is much longer than 4th. See, for example a key by Gressitt & Rondon (1970: 55): *Massicus*: “Antennal segment 3 much longer than 4; 3 and 4 not usually swollen; prothorax not toothed at side”; *Neocerambyx*: “Antennal segment 3 not much longer than 4; 3 and 4 often swollen apically or preapically; prothorax often obtuse or bluntly toothed at side”. But according to Hüdelpohl (1990: 255) several *Neocerambyx* have “antennal segment 3 much longer than 4”. In fact males of *Neocerambyx paris* (Wiedemann, 1821) - the type species of the genus *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 have thin 3rd - 4th antennal joints and 3rd joint much longer than 4th as in the type species of *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867. So, *Neocerambyx* J. Thomson, 1861 = *Massicus* Pascoe, 1867, **syn. n.**

All species of former *Neocerambyx* with really strongly swollen 3rd - 4th antennal joints in males and 3rd joint not much longer than 4th must be separated in a new genus *Bulbocerambyx* **gen. n.** (type species *Neocerambyx grandis* Gahan 1891). Besides the new genus is characterized by regularly oval lateral sides of prothorax without lateral tubercles, 1st antennal joint usually without apical spine, females antennae are often relatively short slightly surpassing elytral middle. *Bulbocerambyx* **gen. n.** includes at least four species: *B. grandis* (Gahan 1891), **comb. n.**, *B. gigas* (Thomson, 1878), **comb. n.**, *B. katarinae* (Holzschuh, 2009), **comb. n.** and *B. vitalisi* (Pic, 1923), **comb. n.**

Neocerambyx J. Thomson, 1861, **sensu n.** includes at least: *N. paris* (Wiedemann, 1821), *N. bakboensis* Miroshnikov, 2018, *N. luzonicus* Hüdelpohl, 1987, *N. pellitus* (Itzinger, 1943), *N. raddei* Blessig, 1872, *N. pubescens* Fisher, 1936, *N. fryi* (Gahan,

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1890), **comb. n.**, *N. intricatus* (Pascoe, 1866), **comb. n.**, *N. ivani* (Miroshnikov, 2017), **comb. n.**, *N. pascoei* (Thomson, 1857), **comb. n.**, *N. philippensis* (Hüdepohl, 1990), **comb. n.**, *N. punctulipennis* (Holzschuh, 2018), **comb. n.**, *N. scapulatus* (Hüdepohl, 1994), **comb. n.**, *N. subregularis* (Schwarzer, 1931), **comb. n.**, *N. sufficiens* (Holzschuh, 2018), **comb. n.**, *N. suffusus* (Gressitt & Rondon, 1970), **comb. n.**, *N. taiwanus* (Makihara & Niisato, 2014), **comb. n.**, *N. trilineatus* (Pic, 1933), **comb. n.**, *N. unicolor* (Gahan, 1906), **comb. n.**, *N. valentinae* (Miroshnikov, 2017), **comb. n.**, *N. venustus* (Pascoe, 1859), **comb. n.**, *N. atratulus* (Holzschuh, 2018), **comb. n.** and *N. regius* (Miroshnikov, 2019), **comb. n.**

Etymology. The new genus name is based on Latin “bulbus” - because of swellings on 3rd - 4th antennal joints.

Neocerambyx elenae Lazarev, sp. n.

Fig. 1

Type locality. China, Hainan Island, Wuzhishan, 18°52'N, 109°40'E, 700 m.

Description. A single female available; body, antennae and legs totally uniformly black; frons and vertex covered with very fine pale pubescence, with very deep central furrow; the distance between antennal tubercles about equal to the length of 1st antennal joint; each tubercle with short but distinct dulled pimple; upper eye lobes separated by the width of each lobe; genae about as long as the apical width of 1st antennal joint and much shorter than lower eye lobe; antennae thin and long, reaching elytral apex; 1st antennal joint strongly widened apically with strong and sharp apical spine; 1st joint a little shorter than 4th, which is about 1.3 times shorter than 3rd; prothorax a little transverse, about 1.1 times shorter than basal width, with regularly oval lateral sides without spines or tubercles; about 1.3 times wider posteriorly, than anteriorly; pronotum coarsely sculptured; with about 8 irregular transverse rugae along middle; scutellum transverse, triangular, about glabrous; elytra parallel-sided, about 2.7 times longer than basal width, smooth, without costae, with very fine indistinct pale pubescence; elytral punctation also indistinct; elytral apices independently rounded; ventral thorax side covered by very dense silver short pubescence; legs long and thin, 1st

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joint of posterior tarsi about as long as 2nd and 3rd combined; abdomen with sparse silver pubescence; last abdominal tergite with deep emargination; last abdominal sternite rounded; body length: 67 mm, body width: 18 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very close to *N. atratulus* (Holzschuh, 2018) described from Darjeeling (North India); but *N. atratulus* has distinct elytral pubescence. Elytra in the new species looks glabrous. First antennal joint in *N. atratulus* without apical spine; pronotal sculpture without transverse central rugae. Other species of the group could be with rather distinct elytral pubescence or if elytral pubescence indistinct with strong spine on 1st antennal joint.

Material. Holotype, female, China, Hainan Island, WuzhiShan, 18°52'N, 109°40'E, 700 m, 11-13.5.2002, Dr. R. Fencł lgt. – ML.

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to my good friend Elena Nikolaevna Piryzeva, an experience art critic who helps me to be on the top of the news of modern art.

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Fig. 1. *Neocerambyx elenae*, sp. n., female, holotype.

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